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#Creativity: Exploring Lay Conceptualizations of Creativity with Twitter Hashtags.

Simon M. Ceh¹, Alexander P. Christensen², Izabela Lebuda^{1,3} & Mathias Benedek¹

¹ Institute of Psychology, University of Graz, Austria

² Psychology and Human Development, Peabody College, Vanderbilt University, USA

³ Institute of Psychology, University of Wroclaw, Poland

Corresponding Author: Simon Ceh (simon.ceh@uni-graz.at)

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20

Abstract

21 The present study explored the public conceptualization of creativity on Twitter through co-
22 listed hashtags associated with *#creativity* in a million tweets. Exploratory Graph Analysis was
23 used to identify a network of semantic clusters, and a pre-trained language model yielded the
24 sentiment of the underlying tweets. The semantic clusters reflect well-known everyday creative
25 domains focused on visual and digital arts, storytelling, and handicraft. Other clusters paid
26 tribute to the role of mindsets, teams, and imagination, feature business and innovation, and
27 stress the importance of creativity for mental health. In addition, we compared the resulting
28 network to one of *#innovation*, which had a higher prevalence of technological clusters relating
29 to areas of digital transformation. Both networks are vastly positive, suggesting that the
30 exhibition of potential and success outweighs tweeting about obstacles and failure. Our study
31 provides a bottom-up socio-cultural snapshot of lay conceptualizations of creativity,
32 highlighting commonalities and differences with theorized conceptualizations.

33 Keywords: Creativity, Innovation, Exploratory Graph Analysis, Semantic Analysis, Twitter

34 **#Creativity: Exploring Lay Conceptualizations of Creativity with Twitter Hashtags.**

35 With the incessant digital revolution, we have come to densely populate digital spaces
36 to discuss what's happening in our lives. A prominent sphere among the many is Twitter, a
37 microblogging platform where users compose short posts (i.e., *tweets*, currently limited to 280
38 characters), often using *hashtags* to emphasize central concepts, people, or events. We
39 frequently use online platforms such as Twitter to consume and contribute creative content (Ceh
40 & Benedek, 2021), and through these platforms, we can gain insights into specific aspects of
41 creative behavior, such as the topical composition of do-it-yourself videos (Ceh & Benedek, in
42 press), or the use of creative linguistic strategies for malevolent purposes (de Saint Laurent et
43 al., 2020). This study focuses on tweets about *#creativity* as an approach to understanding the
44 public conceptualization of creativity on Twitter. It does so by exploring the associative
45 network of creativity in terms of co-listed hashtags analyzed through Exploratory Graph
46 Analysis (Golino & Epskamp, 2017), the sentiment towards the identified semantic clusters,
47 and their prevalence. We further examine the specificity of the creativity network by comparing
48 it to the network of the arguably related concept of innovation, identifying shared and distinct
49 associations of both constructs. This approach aims to add a new perspective to the ontology of
50 creativity – one that is not driven by the conceptual structures of researchers but relies on a
51 public perspective.

52 **Studying Creativity on Twitter**

53 Twitter is one of the most popular social media spheres, attracting close to seven billion
54 monthly visitors (Similarweb, 2022). It is a microblogging service where users can compose
55 short posts (i.e., *tweets*) with a platform-imposed length limit, react to posts, and interact with
56 their authors. One integral part of online social media communication on Twitter and many
57 other platforms is the use of the hash (#) symbol as a prefix to words (i.e., *hashtags*). Hashtags
58 are used to create spaces of shared attention and visibility, making for a specific affordance of

59 digital and social media (Literat & Kligler-Vilenchik, 2019) and enabling discourse without the
60 need for partaking users to be connected through follower networks (Bruns & Burgess, 2015).
61 There are various reasons why people might prefix certain concepts, events, or people with a
62 hash symbol—a process called *Social Tagging* (Huang et al., 2010)— including, for example,
63 an effort to be visibly associated with a certain topic, or the aim to reach people with shared
64 interests (Rauschnabel et al., 2019). The character limit of tweets, combined with the prompt
65 and design of the website to feature trending topics of discourse make for affordances that
66 encourage users to share short takes on what is going on in their lives, partake in the discussion
67 about hot topics, or merely catch up on what others currently share online.

68 Creativity—the ability to generate original and useful products and ideas by
69 recombining existing materials and knowledge (Runco & Jaeger, 2012; Stein, 1953)—has also
70 been investigated in the sphere of Twitter, albeit not very frequently. One study recently
71 described how certain platforms are associated with various domains of creative activity (Ceh
72 & Benedek, 2021): Twitter is among the most frequently used platforms to post creative content
73 online (succumbing only to *Facebook*, *Instagram*, and *Reddit*), and people also use the platform
74 to consume creative content, suggesting that it is a key social network for individuals with an
75 interest in creativity. Another study found that anti-immigration communities on Twitter
76 modify pro-immigration hashtags in a malicious creative act for their common goal (de Saint
77 Laurent et al., 2020), demonstrating that hashtags can be leveraged to gain insight into
78 creativity. However, we are yet to understand how associations of creativity are reflected in
79 online environments.

80 A concept highly related to creativity is innovation. While the former is often viewed as
81 the cognitive process of idea generation, the latter describes the successful implementation of a
82 previously generated idea in business contexts (Amabile & Pratt, 2016). The exact boundaries
83 of both constructs have been, and continue to be debated (Anderson et al., 2014). In a recent

84 study (Reuschke et al., 2021), Twitter data was used to allocate spots for creative
85 entrepreneurship within Brighton (UK) by querying tweets that contained keywords such as
86 *entrepreneur*, or *innovator* in a sample of creative professionals. Interestingly, the largest
87 proportion of tweets from people involved in the creative industry came from meeting spaces
88 (e.g., cafés, and bars), and researchers were able to identify distinct movement/tweet patterns
89 of creative freelancers. This study suggests that Twitter data can be leveraged to gain insight
90 into business-related aspects of creativity, potentially helping to distinguish distinct features
91 within the respective constructs.

92 It has been suggested that creativity researchers could utilize readily available data from
93 online environments to understand creativity in more natural settings, given the inclination to
94 display our creative behaviors on platforms such as YouTube (Ceh & Benedek, in press), but
95 there seems to be a systematic lack of such studies (Mejia et al., 2021). This is a critical gap
96 when considering creativity as a distributed phenomenon, namely as a “social, dialogical, and
97 cultural process” (Literat & Glăveanu, 2018) with a strong focus on the contextual factors of
98 creativity, including the interactions between people, objects, and time (Glăveanu, 2014). A
99 platform like Twitter, which enables interactions between people in shared contexts (i.e.,
100 through hashtags) and allows researchers to investigate the characteristics of these dialogical
101 processes, might bear important insights to close this gap. While Twitter is not fully
102 representative of the general population (e.g., representing younger and more urban cohorts;
103 Mislove et al., 2011; Wojcik & Hughes, 2019), its content is often a central source in
104 mainstream media coverage (Moon & Hadley, 2014; Paulussen & Harder, 2014). As such,
105 scientific studies investigating social media outlets may be of relevance to populations beyond
106 the respective platform borders.

107 **Scientific and Public Conceptualization of Creativity**

108 Over the last decades, there have been various approaches to harness large-scale
109 analyses of text databases to better understand the multi-faceted construct of creativity.
110 Jordanous and Keller (2016) constructed a corpus based on relevant work from scholars in the
111 field and compared it to a set of non-creativity-related scientific publications, identifying
112 keywords that are important in creativity research. These keywords (the top three were *thinking*,
113 *process*, and *innovation*) were then clustered to inform fourteen dimensions of creativity (e.g.,
114 *social interaction and communication*), demonstrating how text analysis techniques can be
115 applied to investigate complex concepts such as creativity. Similarly, another study investigated
116 4,575 papers on creativity research and arrived at five main topics (e.g., *organizational-level*
117 *creativity, pathology and physiology of creativity*; Zhang et al., 2015). Yet another study
118 showcased a dozen major trends in creativity research, linking them to eminent scholars in the
119 respective clusters who act as driving factors for their advancement (Mejia et al., 2021). This
120 study also identified creativity research in the context of digitalization as a transversal topic,
121 permeating areas of scholarly interest, with small, dedicated subtopics allocated around digital
122 media. This is in line with digital transition theory, which posits that human creativity is co-
123 evolving with technology, impacting cognitive, individual, and sociocultural aspects of
124 creativity (Bruno & Canina, 2019), and thus implying relevance for all areas of creativity
125 research. Most recently, De-Marchis and Shchebetenko (2022) identified leading journals,
126 frequently cited articles, and influential scholars, as well as the interconnectedness of topics
127 within European creativity research.

128 These publications have dealt with and extended our understanding of the outlets, topics,
129 progress, as well as catalyzers of scientific research about creativity, and – like explicit theories
130 of creativity – reflect a scientific understanding rather than a public view. On the contrary,
131 implicit/naïve theories of creativity reflect beliefs about creativity that are expressed by
132 laypeople. Scholarly investigations of lay beliefs have identified terms and concepts commonly
133 attributed to creativity and creative people, such as non-entrenchment, aesthetic

134 taste/imagination, perspicacity, and inquisitiveness (Sternberg, 1985), uncovered cultural
135 differences related to understandings of creativity (Runco & Johnson, 2010), investigated the
136 perception of malevolent creativity (Cropley et al., 2014), and examined how expert-theories
137 such as the four-C-model of creativity (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2009), or the adaptor-innovator
138 theory (Kirton, 1976) are conceived by non-experts (Gralewski & Karwowski, 2018; Kaufman
139 & Beghetto, 2013). In total, these studies indicate that scientific evidence and lay
140 understandings of creativity do not always align. Instead, research on laypeople beliefs about
141 creativity has helped to uncover a wide range of misconceptions (cf. Ritter & Rietzschel, 2017),
142 such as bias towards artistic fields (Glăveanu, 2014; Paulhus et al., 2002), lower emphasis on
143 usefulness / value in creativity judgments (Weisberg et al., 2021), and overestimation of insight
144 and underestimation of persistence for the creative process (Lucas & Nordgren, 2022), all of
145 which are best reflected in the ubiquity of creativity myths—popular but incorrect beliefs about
146 creativity (e.g., Benedek et al., 2021; Kim, 2019; Plucker et al., 2010; Ritter & Rietzschel,
147 2017).

148 Given that such beliefs about creativity form the basis of agentic actions (Karwowski et
149 al., 2019), influencing whether somebody decides to start with and persist on creative ideation
150 (Lucas & Nordgren, 2020), when to behave creatively (Baas et al., 2015), and how to assess
151 one's creative ideas and performance (Sidi et al., 2020), we argue that capturing the digital
152 footprint of creativity on Twitter could provide an insightful representation of themes and
153 beliefs related to creativity in a period of digital transition, helping to uncover what people think
154 and value about the construct.

155 **Aims of the Study**

156 This study uses readily available data from the online platform Twitter to gain a better
157 understanding of the public representation of creativity by contributing a bottom-up
158 perspective to the conceptualization of the construct. The main aim of this study is to identify

159 the semantic structure of concepts associated with *creativity* as evidenced by the network of
160 frequently associated hashtags in tweets regarding *#creativity*. To this end, we investigate
161 which hashtags frequently co-occur within tweets containing “*#creativity*” and compute a
162 network with the typically associated hashtags using Exploratory Graph Analysis (Golino &
163 Epskamp, 2017). Thus, the concept map results from an implicit approach as it is based on
164 identifying close associations within the concept rather than by asking people explicitly how
165 they conceptualize creativity. In addition to obtaining the concept structure reflecting
166 common associations, we investigate the sentiment of individual hashtags and the resulting
167 network clusters with a pre-trained and finetuned language model (Loureiro et al., 2022). Our
168 study will thus provide a new perspective on the public’s conception of creativity, showing
169 how this construct is represented and valued in a digital environment. To explore the
170 specificity of the findings, we compare the network of *#creativity* to a network for the related
171 concept of *#innovation*.

172 **Methods**

173 Materials required to reproduce the experiment are available on the Open Science
174 Framework: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/2SBCD>

175 **Data Acquisition and Preprocessing**

176 This study used *academictwitteR* (Barrie & Ho, 2021; v.0.3.1) in *R* (R Core Team, 2022;
177 v. 4.2.1) to access the *Twitter API v.2* endpoints to collect data. We queried *#creativity* and
178 *#innovation* over five years (2017-2022) and extracted English tweets (as classified by Twitter).
179 Figure 1 shows the exact search queries and data processing steps until the central analyses.
180 The query for *#creativity* yielded a total of 1,971,609 tweets. As *#innovation* is more prevalent
181 on Twitter, we limited the number of tweets about *#innovation* to 1080/day, resulting in a total
182 of 1,972,080 tweets, thereby closely matching the number of *#creativity* tweets in the same
183 period. In the first step, tweets with sensitive content, as classified by Twitter, were removed.

184 Then, we performed lowercasing, identified hashtags, removed URLs, mentioned users,
185 punctuation, and superfluous whitespaces, relying on the packages *tidytext* (Silge & Robinson,
186 2016; v.0.3.4) and *stringr* (Wickham, 2022; v.1.4.1). Because we were interested in the co-
187 occurrence of hashtags within our queries, we removed tweets from the data that would solely
188 contain the respective queried hashtag. We double-checked the language of the tweets using
189 *fastText* (Mouselimis, 2022; v.1.0.3). We then randomly selected a maximum of 60 tweets per
190 author in the 5-year period (reflecting an average of one tweet/month) to avoid distortion by
191 overly active users. After these steps, 1,029,803 tweets remained for *#creativity*, and 1,079,919
192 for *#innovation*.

193 EGA

194 Exploratory Graph Analysis (Golino & Epskamp, 2017) is a method from the field of
195 network psychometrics to estimate the dimensionality of constructs. The models result from the
196 application of a network estimation method (e.g., Triangulated Maximally Filtered Graph;
197 TMFG; Massara et al., 2017) and a community detection algorithm (e.g., Walktrap; Pons &
198 Latapy, 2006), yielding *nodes* (i.e., items) and *edges* (i.e., the relationship between nodes). A
199 set of connected nodes is referred to as a *community* and is equivalent to a latent factor (Golino
200 & Epskamp, 2017). EGA is a data-driven method that does not require guidance from the
201 researcher (Christensen et al., 2019), outperforms the most widely used factor analytic
202 techniques (Golino et al., 2022), and is easily interpretable. We used the *EGAnet* package
203 (Golino & Christensen, 2022; v.1.2.4) to apply EGA to the preprocessed datasets of *#creativity*
204 and *#innovation*. Using the *tm* package (Feinerer et al., 2008; v.0.7-8), corpora of the hashtags
205 were constructed. We built a document-term-matrix (dtm) for each dataset and reduced the
206 maximum sparsity to 99.5%. The sparsity criterion is an arbitrary step chosen by the researchers
207 and leads to the loss of sparse data. In this case, the aim was to extract general and prevalent
208 hashtags, thus disregarding highly specific content. We did not include the respective seed

209 hashtags (*#creativity* for the *#creativity*-network and *#innovation* for the *#innovation*-network)
210 when running EGA on the remaining extracted hashtags (*#creativity*: 841,568 tweets;
211 *#innovation*: 816,945 tweets). Given that their presence was unconditional for a tweet to be
212 included in the final data set, including the seed would have produced an artifact (i.e., the
213 allocation to one specific cluster).

214 *Network Estimation*

215 As a network estimation method, we used Triangulated Maximally Filtered Graph
216 (TMFG; Massara et al., 2017), which has demonstrated better accuracy than the more common
217 GLASSO approach in text data (Golino et al., 2022). TMFG structurally constrains the resulting
218 network into cliques of three and four nodes, each. The cliques are initially formed when their
219 sum of correlations is higher than the average correlation in the correlation matrix (Christensen,
220 Cardillo, et al., 2022). Spearman correlation was used to account for skewed data (Isvoranu &
221 Epskamp, 2021). The algorithm proceeds to iteratively select unconnected nodes and add them
222 to a clique of three nodes based on the highest correlations until all nodes are assigned.

223 *Community Detection*

224 We applied the Walktrap algorithm (Pons & Latapy, 2006) to identify clusters within
225 the network. The algorithm initiates a random walk ($n = 4$ steps) from each node (i.e., hashtag)
226 to connected nodes. Nodes with larger edge weights (i.e., higher Spearman correlation) are
227 more likely traversed. Modularity is then used to form the optimal number of communities
228 (Christensen et al., 2021). To check the goodness of fit for the manually chosen community
229 labels, we ran zero-shot classification (Yin et al., 2019) using a pre-trained model
230 (*facebook/bart-large-mnli*). Zero-shot classification allows for testing the probability of a string
231 (here: sequence of hashtags from a community) belonging to a list of class names (here:
232 community labels). All communities of hashtags were assigned the intended label, with scores

233 > .86, suggesting a close fit between the hashtags and the chosen labels (see Table S1 in the
234 Supplementary Materials).

235 *Unique Variable Analysis.*

236 We additionally performed Unique Variable Analysis (Christensen, Garrido, et al.,
237 2022) to detect whether there are locally dependent hashtags in the networks. The approach
238 works by applying a network estimation method and computing a network measure called
239 weighted topological overlap (wTO; Nowick et al., 2009; Zhang & Horvath, 2005) that
240 quantifies node similarity using the strength of the edge (i.e., partial correlation) that connects
241 them as well as the edges they share. Using only the non-zero (absolute) weighted topological
242 overlap values, a threshold was applied with values $\geq .25$ suggesting that a pair of hashtags are
243 locally dependent. These dependencies may indicate semantically similar hashtags, but also
244 strategically chosen hashtag patterns (e.g., to increase visibility; Wang et al., 2016). The list of
245 identified hashtags is provided in the Supplementary Materials (see Table S2).

246 **Sentiment Analysis**

247 With the introduction of the Transformer, a network architecture based solely on multi-
248 headed self-attention mechanisms (Vaswani et al., 2017), and the development of language
249 models such as BERT (i.e., Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers; Devlin
250 et al., 2018) and its derivatives (e.g., RoBERTa; Liu et al., 2019), new standards have been
251 achieved for various natural language processing applications. Using *Python* (v.3.10), through
252 the open-source library Transformers (Wolf et al., 2020), we accessed a RoBERTa-base (Liu
253 et al., 2019) masked language model, which was trained on 124 million tweets (Loureiro et al.,
254 2022) and finetuned for sentiment analysis using the TweetEval benchmark (Barbieri et al.,
255 2020). The chosen model (*cardiffnlp/twitter-roberta-base-sentiment-latest*) is diachronically
256 specialized, meaning that it is updated with *recent* data from Twitter to account for temporal
257 shifts that impact the classification of sequences (Loureiro et al., 2022). Consequently, its

258 context strongly overlaps with the present goal of application to contemporary Twitter data. It
259 identifies tweets as being positive, neutral, or negative with a probability estimator for each
260 class that accumulates to one. We analyzed the sentiment of all tweets that would contain at
261 least one of the hashtags from the final network structure (*#creativity*: 841,568 tweets;
262 *#innovation*: 816,945 tweets), computing a positivity ratio for each hashtag as

$$263 \quad pos.\,ratio = \frac{n(positive\,tweets) - n(negative\,tweets)}{n(positive\,tweets) + n(neutral\,tweets) + n(negative\,tweets)}$$

264 at the overall network, cluster, and hashtag level.

265 **Results**

266 **#Creativity**

267 *Network Clusters*

268 Figure 2-A presents the estimated *#creativity*-network. The nodes represent the hashtags
269 that commonly co-occurred with *#creativity* and the edges represent their relatedness through
270 Spearman correlation. EGA revealed nine clusters (i.e., topics) with a total of 101 hashtags.
271 Topic A represents various *Arts*-related concepts: Besides hashtags such as *#art*, *#artist*, or
272 *#artwork*, this cluster contains a wide range of everyday creative behaviors stemming from the
273 creative domains of visual art (e.g., *#photography*, *#video*, *#digitalart*) and handicraft (e.g.,
274 *#diy*). Topic B is about *Branding*, mentioning activities (e.g., *#graphicdesign*) and tools (e.g.,
275 *#photoshop*) and how they can be used for *#(digital)marketing*. Topic C features *Mindsets*
276 associated with *#creativity* using hashtags such as *#motivation*, *#inspiration*, *#growth*, and
277 further includes *#quotes* relating to creativity. Seemingly, these aspects relate to *#success* in
278 *#love*, *#life*, and at *#work*. Topic D represents *Entrepreneurship*, bridging the gap to
279 *#innovation*, *#business*, and *#technology*. Topic E is specifically dedicated to *Storytelling*,
280 serving as the mouthpiece of the *#writingcommunity* and *#podcast* enthusiasts, and includes
281 specific writing styles such as *#poetry*. Topic F, *Education*, is dedicated to *#skills*, *#learning*,

282 *#kids*, and *#play*. Topic G, *Music and Culture*, is a small cluster related to *#music*, but also
283 features hashtags such as *#diversity*, *#community*, *#arts*, and *#culture*, reflecting the discussion
284 of meta-themes related to creativity. Topic H points to the role of creativity for *Well-being*,
285 specifically, *#mentalhealth*, stressing the importance of *#mindfulness* in times of the *#covid19*
286 pandemic. Finally, Topic I is a small cluster of hashtags relating to *Teamwork*, emphasizing the
287 importance of *#curiosity*, *#criticalthinking*, and *#communication* for creativity.

288 ***Prevalence and Time Trends***

289 To better understand the general prevalence of these clusters, and their prevalence over
290 time, we allocated each tweet to one or multiple cluster(s) based on the hashtags it contained.
291 Overall, the most prevalent hashtag was *#art*, followed by *#innovation*, *#creative*, *#design*, and
292 *#inspiration*. Topic A, relating to *Arts*, was the most prevalent topic, accounting for 27.19% of
293 the tweets containing *#creativity*. Hashtags from the topic *Wellbeing* co-occurred with
294 *#creativity* in only 2.98% of all tweets, thus forming the least prevalent topic. Figure 4 shows
295 the relative prevalence of the *#creativity* network clusters over time. In general, the formed
296 clusters remained relatively stable over the five years. For *Wellbeing*, we observed spikes in
297 2020-04 (7.93%) and 2021-01 (7.21%), indicating how infection waves of *#covid19* impacted
298 tweets containing *#creativity*. At the same time, 2020-04 (31.42%) and 2020-05 (31.66%) were
299 the times with the highest relative prevalence of tweets about *Arts*.

300 ***Sentiment***

301 For each tweet, we also computed the sentiment. Most tweets were classified as positive
302 (n = 481,582; 57.22%) or neutral (n = 334,672; 39.77%), and only a small share was classified
303 as negative (n = 25,314; 3.01%). Given that these tweets inform the estimated network of
304 hashtag-co-occurrences, we computed the positivity ratio on a hashtag level (see Figure 4).
305 *#Happiness*, *#fun*, *#love*, *#wellbeing*, and *#inspire* made up the top five most positive hashtags
306 in the *#creativity* network. In contrast, *#logo*, *#writerslife*, *#covid19*, *#digitalart*, and

307 *#photoshop* were the least positive hashtags. However, this is mostly due to a relatively high
308 proportion of neutral rather than negative tweets, again underlining the general positivity of the
309 network. We screened the tweets containing *#covid19*, finding that they mostly dealt with
310 coping with the challenges imposed by the pandemic rather than suffering from it.
311 Consequently, the clusters that were estimated from the hashtags were positive, with an average
312 positivity ratio of 0.54 ($SD = 0.07$). *Mindset* and *Education* (0.61) were the most positive
313 clusters, and *Storytelling* (0.42) was the least positive cluster. Table 1 provides detailed
314 descriptive statistics for the *#creativity* clusters, including information on their prevalence and
315 sentiment.

316 **#Innovation**

317 *Network Clusters*

318 Figure 2-B presents the estimated *#innovation*-network. Nine clusters with a total of 91
319 hashtags form the network. Topic A, *Digital Transformation*, refers to the computational
320 advances in dealing with *#data*, involving hashtags such as *#machinelearning*, and
321 *#artificialintelligence*, while also relating to the Internet (*#iot*; i.e., *Internet of Things*),
322 *#cybersecurity*, and *#automation*. Topic B, *Technology and Design*, is about recent advances in
323 *#technology*, emphasizing the role of *#creativity* for *#design*. Topic C, *Fintech*, is coined by
324 *#cryptocurrency* and the *#disruption* of the financial market, further stressing hashtags such as
325 *#ideas* and *#community*. Topic D, *Entrepreneurship*, features *#entrepreneurship*, *#startups*, and
326 how *#success* cases may serve as *#inspiration* for *#business* plans. Topic E, *Leadership and*
327 *Culture*, appears to be more strongly focused on *#management* aspects, involving *#strategy*,
328 *#culture*, and *#diversity*. Topic F, *Education*, features *#learning*, but also relates to *#research*
329 and *#science*. Topic G, *Branding*, relates to *#marketing* on *#socialmedia*, and, more generally,
330 *#ecommerce*. Topic H, *Health*, covers technological aspects of *#health*, such as *#medtech*, and
331 *#digitalhealth*, and includes *#covid19*. Finally, Topic I, *Sustainability*, is a small cluster with

332 *#energy* and *#climatechange*, reflecting the focus on *#sustainable* innovation as a remedy to
333 the current global threats.

334 *Prevalence and Time Trends*

335 Table 1 provides additional information on the prevalence and positivity of *#innovation*
336 clusters and Figure S1 illustrates the relative prevalence of *#innovation*-clusters over time.
337 *Digital Transformation* contained the highest number of hashtags (n = 21) but accounted only
338 for the second most tweets with an average prevalence of 21.75%. *Technology & Design* was
339 the most prevalent topic, accounting for more than one-quarter of all tweets containing
340 *#innovation* (26.37%). *Sustainability* was the least prevalent topic, contributing 2.91% of the
341 tweets. For *Health* (5.02%), there is a spike in relative prevalence for 2020-04 (13.17%), just
342 like for the *Wellbeing*-topic in the *#creativity*-network. These relative increases, which conform
343 to surges in Covid-19 case numbers, indicate the temporal sensitivity of the chosen approach
344 and the need for creativity and innovation to cope with the pandemic. Concerning the
345 prevalence of single hashtags, we found *#technology* to be most prevalent, followed by *#tech*,
346 *#business*, *#leadership*, and *#startup* (Figure S2).

347 *Sentiment*

348 Overall, the network of hashtags co-occurring with *#innovation* is again very positive,
349 with most tweets being classified as positive (442,787; 54.20%) or neutral (353,875, 43.32%),
350 and only a few as negative (20,283, 2.48%). While forming the smallest cluster in the network,
351 and being the least prevalent, *Sustainability* was also the most positive (pos. ratio = 0.54).
352 *Digital Transformation* was the least positive (0.33) of all clusters ($M = 0.46$, $SD = 0.07$). Figure
353 S2 depicts the prevalence and positivity of all hashtags from the *#innovation*-network (see also
354 Table 1). Interestingly, 35 of the 91 hashtags are also part of the *#creativity* network. Among
355 the 91 hashtags, *#sustainable* was the most positive one, with *#community*, *#collaboration*,
356 *#diversity*, and *#inspiration* completing the top five. We also compared the relative positivity

357 of the two networks on the hashtag level using a *Welch* two-sample t-test, finding that the
358 network of creativity ($M = 0.52$, $SD = 0.11$) was more positive than the network of innovation
359 ($M = 0.44$, $SD = 0.11$; $t = 5.11$, $p < .001$).

360 Discussion

361 This study set out to capitalize on a large amount of data from Twitter to extract a public
362 conceptualization of *#creativity*. Using Exploratory Graph Analysis, we found that creativity is
363 represented through nine distinct semantic clusters, including some of which correspond to
364 creative domains creative writing, music, and visual arts, whereas others refer to large meta-
365 topics such as wellbeing, education, and entrepreneurship. The constituting hashtags involved
366 concrete behaviors (e.g., writing, drawing) and outcomes (e.g., video, book, blog, podcast),
367 indicated socio-cultural value (e.g., culture, diversity, and fun), and referred to psychological
368 concepts (e.g., motivation, imagination, and mindset). In addition, interesting nuances have
369 become apparent from exploring the prevalence and sentiment associated with the topics and
370 underlying hashtags, which we discuss below.

371 The Representation of Creative Domains on Twitter

372 The estimated network of *#creativity* contains various topics and hashtags relating to
373 creative behaviors. The most prevalent cluster is *Arts*, which entails components of visual arts,
374 including moving and still images (e.g., *#video*, *#photography*), *#digitalart*, and *#animation*,
375 but also incorporates handicrafts (e.g., *#diy*; do-it-yourself). Besides different types of artistic
376 creativity, *Arts* also incorporates central terminology such as *#artwork*, *#artist*, *#artists*, and
377 *#artistsontwitter*. The cluster *Branding* adds additional activities and fields specifically related
378 to design (e.g., *#graphicdesign*). *Storytelling* is dedicated to *#writing* and features *#podcast* as
379 a substantial and trending modality of narration. Finally, the network also contains a cluster that
380 features *#music*. The results regarding the represented creative domains are consistent with a
381 previous study that found Twitter to be associated with most creative domains and social

382 creativity, in particular (Ceh & Benedek, 2021). The latter becomes evident in the presence of
383 various hashtags that unmistakably go beyond individual perspectives on creativity (e.g.,
384 *#community*, *#diversity*, *#leadership*). The findings further suggest that while certain creative
385 domains are well represented on Twitter (i.e., writing, visual arts, and design), other popular
386 domains such as performing arts, creative cooking, or interior and garden design, play a lesser
387 role in tweets about *#creativity*. This might be due to various reasons other than a lower general
388 prevalence, such as that the structure and the demographics of the platform might benefit some
389 creative topics more than others, the popularity of other platforms for specific types of creative
390 content, or that some creative activities might be less commonly communicated (through
391 hashtags). Still, considering the ubiquitous use of digital environments like Twitter (cf. Ceh &
392 Benedek, 2021), it can be assumed that the present study follows an ecologically valid approach
393 to study conceptualizations of *#creativity* that incorporates the influences of digitalization. This
394 study adds another perspective to creativity in digital contexts and suggests that creativity
395 research needs to better acknowledge the increasing role of digital creativity in our everyday
396 lives, which is a calling for more strongly focusing the assessment of digital creativity as an
397 aspect of everyday creative behavior.

398 Artistic fields are closely linked to creativity and sometimes even overrepresented in lay
399 conceptions (i.e., arts bias; Benedek et al., 2021; Glăveanu, 2014; Patston et al., 2018). The
400 present study suggests that the arts, especially visual art, also play a central role in this online
401 digital sphere, as 1) many of the most prevalent hashtags associated with creativity directly
402 refer to the arts and 2) activities related to arts and especially visual arts have a dominating
403 presence in the network. The substantial focus on visual arts is in line with previous findings
404 showing that most popular online platforms are strongly associated with visual arts and users
405 actively contribute visual art content (Ceh & Benedek, 2021). However, while art plays an
406 important role, six out of the nine semantic clusters had a different focus, including *Learning*
407 *& Education*, *Business*, and *Health*, pointing to a rather differentiated conceptualization of

408 creativity on Twitter. For example, our results may reflect the democratization of the arts and a
409 general shift in arts thinking “from genius to entrepreneur” (Rocavert, 2016, p. 234), as is
410 reflected in the present connection between creativity and aspects of branding, marketing,
411 business, and innovation.

412 **From DIY to Storytelling: a Multifaceted View of Everyday Creativity on Twitter**

413 Similarly, the democratization of creativity and the association of the platform with
414 social creativity (cf. Figure 3 in Ceh & Benedek, 2021) is provided through hashtags such as
415 *#diy* (i.e., *do-it-yourself*), and *#amwriting*. DIY practices resemble the production of original
416 and effective products in everyday contexts (Ceh & Benedek, in press; Fox, 2013) by amateurs
417 and expert-amateurs (Arthurs et al., 2018; Kuznetsov & Paulos, 2010) and reflect a multitude
418 of everyday creative behaviors, such as crafting decorations for festive events and refurbishing
419 furniture (Ceh & Benedek, in press). Tweeting under this hashtag allows everyday creatives to
420 generate and exchange collective knowledge through social interaction about the products and
421 processes relating to DIY. Likewise, *#amwriting*, where the “am” stands for amateur, is a way
422 for writers who might not be publicly recognized but are actively involved in a writing project
423 to connect with other writers and share experiences, advice, and support. Possibly, the self-
424 identification as non-professional may lead to evaluation that is more strongly focused on the
425 development of skills rather than on judging products. In general, the focus on the community
426 (e.g., *#writingcommunity*) and publicly visible tagging of one’s hobbyist status reflects the
427 willingness to engage in discourse among people with shared interests and skillsets, thus
428 reflecting common motives for hashtag use (Rauschnabel et al., 2019) and sociocultural
429 situatedness of creative participation (Glăveanu, 2015; Literat & Glăveanu, 2018). As such,
430 these amateur spheres created within a huge environment can be conducive to sharing and
431 developing creative knowledge as they focus on craft rather than economic value (van Dijk,
432 2014). Noteworthy, the cluster related to writing, *Storytelling*, was also the least positive

433 regarding the sentiment. After screening tweets that use *#amwriting*, we found that this general
434 finding may indeed be partially explained by the struggle that (amateur) writers experience and
435 vocalize. Research suggests that using writing as a means to cope with negative emotion should
436 aim at distraction (writing about something else) rather than venting (writing about the cause;
437 Drake et al., 2011; Drake & Winner, 2012). However, discussing the roots of problems such as
438 *writer's block* (e.g., Rose, 2011) may allow for the exchange of helpful advice and thus be a
439 means of problem-solving that may be beneficial for personal creativity in the longer run.

440 **Sentiment and Creativity-Beliefs**

441 In this context, it seems especially relevant that the network of creativity was vastly
442 positive, as most tweets appear to draw from positive vocabulary. Indeed, creativity is robustly
443 associated with a positive mood (Baas et al., 2008), and fun and enjoyment are key motives for
444 creative behavior (Benedek et al., 2020), as is bringing pleasure to others (Ceh & Benedek,
445 2021). Yet, it also seems possible that Twitter users are more likely to share successful news
446 about creative engagements, or value (the potential of) creativity in various contexts rather than
447 sharing how they struggle or fail, or dislike creativity, in general. This selective exposure may
448 support inadequate lay beliefs that creativity merely results from spontaneous insight or
449 giftedness rather than cognitive challenge and persistence (Baas et al., 2015; Benedek et al.,
450 2021; Karwowski et al., 2020; Lucas & Nordgren, 2022). Further down the line, this positivity
451 bias may lead to a sense of discouragement in times of personal struggle with creativity, which
452 may cause people to question their creative potential and undermine their motivation to engage
453 in creative activities. Here, dedicated communities that accept and value the difficulty of being
454 creative might be the spheres to regain momentum. Hence, generally positive reports about
455 creativity can have varied effects.

456 Complementary, Twitter users who tweet under the hashtag *#creativity* also express
457 their beliefs about creativity. The present network included *#talent* and *#growth* as the central

458 indicators of holding either a fixed or malleable creative *#mindset* (Karwowski, 2013;
459 Karwowski et al., 2019). These beliefs have a regulatory function and translate into interest and
460 engagement in creativity (O'Connor et al., 2013; Pretz & Nelson, 2017), as can also be derived
461 from the linkage with *#motivation* in the *mindset* cluster. *#Mindset* and *#growth* are closely
462 related to *#success*, which is in line with the results of scientific explorations: People who
463 perceive creativity as prone to intentional development tend to be more successful in creative
464 endeavors (e.g., Hass et al., 2016; O'Connor et al., 2013; Puente-Díaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2017).
465 On the other hand, *#talent* was more strongly associated with musical creativity than mindset.
466 Perceiving creativity as an inborn talent is part of the entity theory of creativity. The relation
467 with domain-specific creativity presented an interesting clue to better understanding the implicit
468 theory of creativity, letting us suspect that the specificity of the field of activity could
469 differentiate creative self-beliefs.

470 **Comparing Creativity with Innovation**

471 To examine the specificity of the obtained *#creativity* network, we compared it to the
472 *#innovation* network, which is viewed as a related yet reasonably distinct concept. Indeed, the
473 networks showed some overlaps, for instance in terms of 35 shared hashtags, feeding into four
474 strongly overlapping clusters for Business, Branding, Education, and Health, but also differed
475 substantially. Tweets about *#creativity* more often included specific behaviors and referred to
476 psychological aspects of the creative process and the individual, such as the role of motivation.
477 In contrast, innovation seems to more strongly reflect the economic factors of the outside world.
478 This difference is even visible in the shared context of health: While the association between
479 *#creativity* and *#health* deals with *#wellbeing*, the association between *#innovation* and *#health*
480 reflects advancing medical technology to improve healthcare. The prevalence of both clusters
481 was positively affected by the Covid-19 pandemic: Interestingly, for *#creativity*, this increase
482 in prevalence did not sustain, reflecting a more immediate reaction to Covid-19, potentially

483 related to personal efforts of coping with the pandemic. Indeed, studies have shown that creative
484 behaviors were positively affected by the pandemic (Karwowski et al., 2021; Lopez-Persem et
485 al., 2022) and it seems plausible that sharing creative artifacts and emphasizing the role of
486 creativity for wellbeing may have served a regulatory function. (e.g., Ceh & Benedek, in press;
487 Karwowski et al., 2021; Lopez-Persem et al., 2022)For *#innovation*, the increased prevalence
488 was more prolonged, which may reflect more sustained discussions of tackling Covid-19
489 through technology. Similarly, while the role of motivation seems highly relevant for the
490 creative process in *#creativity*, motivation is strongly implicated in business success for
491 *#innovation*. These differences also occur for the respective clusters relating to branding, where
492 digital marketing is connected to the creative activity and profession for *#creativity* (e.g.,
493 *#graphicdesign*), versus to the business implications for *#innovation* (e.g., *#retail*). For
494 creativity, the *Branding* cluster was closely linked to the cluster of *Entrepreneurship*, which
495 also features *#innovation* as the second-most prevalent hashtag throughout the network,
496 indicating how businesses are a central way for creators to externalize their and capitalize from
497 their creative work (e.g., Reuschke et al., 2021). For the network of *#innovation*, the *Technology*
498 *and Design* cluster features *#creativity* as the 12th-most prevalent hashtag together with terms
499 like *#future* and *#development*, indicating that creativity may be considered a key to sustained
500 and future-proof prevail of businesses. The network of *#innovation* additionally features several
501 unique topics related to technological advancements, such as *#cryptocurrency* and *#ai*, which
502 are not present in the network of *#creativity*. At the same time, *#creativity* more strongly
503 incorporates social linkage, through hashtags such as *#community*. For *#innovation*, these
504 aspects seem more concentrated on business management and the crypto community. Together,
505 these differences between *#creativity* and *#innovation* are largely consistent with established
506 theoretical conceptualizations viewing innovation as creativity applied in an economical
507 context and residing at the level of companies rather than individuals (Amabile, 1988; Amabile
508 & Pratt, 2016; Edwards-Schachter et al., 2015; Hughes et al., 2018).

509 **Conclusions, Limitations, and Future Directions**

510 The present study harnessed Twitter data to provide a unique perspective on the contemporary
511 public conceptualization of creativity. With the digital transformation and the immense
512 popularity of Twitter, we can consider this digital environment a naturalistic setting with a fair
513 degree of representation for the English-speaking, digitally native population. That is to say,
514 Twitter certainly has a specific demographic pattern, for example, US-American Twitter users
515 are overly representative of the young and urban population (Mislove et al., 2011; Wojcik &
516 Hughes, 2019) and as such, the present study cannot infer a conceptualization of creativity by
517 the general population. However, with billions of monthly visitors on Twitter and tweets
518 regularly making news (e.g., Moon & Hadley, 2014), this study offers a snapshot of lay
519 conceptualizations of creativity with the potential to impact beliefs and mindsets about
520 creativity that affect behavior outside of the Twitter realm. The results inform us about the
521 socio-cultural embedding of creativity and the transformation of creative practices in a digitally
522 evolving and technology-driven world. The approach employed in this study offers a means to
523 monitor the public conceptualization of and interest in creativity in a time-sensitive way. It
524 enables us to observe changes and identify trends, and thereby understand who contemporary
525 creative catalysts are. For example, it will be interesting to see how the currently surging interest
526 in machine learning and artificial intelligence - as we found in the network of innovation - will
527 be transforming to become a common digital creative practice in contexts of graphic design or
528 digital artwork, writing, music, and perhaps many other fields. Hence, while digital
529 technologies are thought to have massive effects on everyday creative behavior, they also imply
530 unprecedented means to study digital footprints of creative behavior at scale.

531

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Figures

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Figure 1. Data collection and preprocessing steps.

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811 *Notes. #c = creativity query; #i = innovation query. If applicable, the numbers of tweets lost*
 812 *per step are annotated. The final number of tweets for #creativity = 1.029.803; for #innovation*
 813 *= 1.079.919. The use of special libraries/packages is indicated in brackets.* The query for*
 814 *#innovation was limited to 1080 results/day. ** This was the case for tweets that were removed*
 815 *after being reported for copyright infringement. *** This is related to the use of special*
 816 *characters such as in “#créativity”.*

Figure 3. Relative prevalence of #creativity-topics over time.

Figure 4. Sentiment and prevalence for hashtags contained in #creativity-network tweets.

Notes. Bar labels denote the number of tweets with the respective hashtag. Sentiment bars relate to the number of times a hashtag was used in a positive/neutral/negative tweet. The total number of hashtag occurrences is higher than the total number of tweets given that some tweets contain multiple hashtags.

Tables

Table 1. Overview of #creativity- and #innovation-clusters.

Network	Prevalence			Sentiment				Top-3 Hashtags		
	Hashtags	Tweets	Prevalence (%)	Pos.	Neu.	Neg.	Ratio	Most prevalent	Most positive	Highest network loading
A: Arts	21	390707	27.19	196120	186970	7617	0.48	#art, #creative, #artist	#beauty, #nature, #create	#artwork, #artist, #art
B: Branding	15	222022	15.45	105064	112004	4954	0.45	#design, #marketing, #branding	#design, #digitalmarketing, #marketing	#branding, #graphicdesign, #marketing
C: Mindset	15	198565	13.82	125922	67531	5112	0.61	#inspiration, #love, #motivation	#happiness, #love, #inspire	#motivation, #success, #quotes
D: Entrepreneurship	14	243546	16.95	136785	99352	7409	0.53	#innovation, #business, #leadership	#stem, #innovation, #technology	#entrepreneurship, #technology, #innovation
E: Storytelling	11	126257	8.79	59087	61480	5690	0.42	#writing, #amwriting, #writingcommunity	#books, #podcast, #storytelling	#writing, #writerslife, #amwriting
F: Education	7	90898	6.33	57876	30862	2160	0.61	#imagination, #education, #fun	#fun, #kids, #play	#learning, #kids, #education
G: Music and Culture	6	70308	4.89	43090	25520	1698	0.59	#music, #arts, #culture	#community, #talent, #diversity	#culture, #arts, #art
H: Wellbeing	6	42790	2.98	25341	16040	1409	0.56	#mentalhealth, #mindfulness, #wellbeing	#wellbeing, #health, #mindfulness	#wellbeing, #mentalhealth, #health
I: Teamwork	6	51724	3.60	31302	19412	1010	0.59	#collaboration, #teamwork, #communication	#teamwork, #collaboration, #curiosity	#communication, #criticalthinking, #collaboration
#Innovation	Hashtags	Tweets	Prevalence (%)	Pos.	Neu.	Neg.	Ratio	Most prevalent	Most positive	Highest network loading
A: Digital Transformation	20	322048	21.75	113516	202592	5940	0.33	#iot, #digitaltransformation, #digital	#cloud, #futureofwork, #digitaltransformation	#datascience, #machinelearning, #bigdata
B: Technology and Design	16	390511	26.37	199796	182518	8197	0.49	#technology, #tech, #creativity	#creativity, #3dprinting, #future	#engineering, #technews, #tech
C: Fintech	13	146447	9.89	68035	75168	3244	0.44	#fintech, #blockchain, #collaboration	#community, #collaboration, #crypto	#blockchain, #fintech, #cryptocurrency
D: Entrepreneurship	11	248224	16.76	131439	110786	5999	0.51	#business, #startup, #startups	#inspiration, #success, #growth	#entrepreneur, #success, #startup
E: Leadership and Culture	9	110665	7.47	51564	55037	4064	0.43	#leadership, #strategy, #management	#diversity, #podcast, #leadership	#leadership, #strategy, #business
F: Education	6	81286	5.49	43013	36452	1821	0.51	#science, #education, #research	#stem, #edtech, #learning	#education, #stem, #edtech
G: Branding	6	64135	4.33	26403	36432	1300	0.39	#marketing, #digitalmarketing, #socialmedia	#retail, #ecommerce, #branding	#marketing, #digitalmarketing, #socialmedia
H: Health	6	74401	5.02	35772	36733	1896	0.46	#healthcare, #covid19, #health	#medtech, #healthcare, #digitalhealth	#healthtech, #healthcare, #digitalhealth
I: Sustainability	4	43071	2.91	24371	17753	947	0.54	#sustainability, #energy, #climatechange	#sustainable, #sustainability, #energy	#sustainability, #climatechange, #energy

Notes. Hashtags = number of hashtags that form the respective cluster. Tweets = number of tweets that contain a hashtag from this cluster. Pos. = Positive, Neu. = Neutral, Neg. = Negative. Ratio = (Number of Tweets classified as positive – Number of Tweets classified as negative) / (Total number of Tweets).

Supplementary Material

Table S1. Results of zero-shot classification regarding label fit using the facebook/bart-large-mnli language model.

#Creativity-Clusters: Hashtag-Sequence	#1 Label	Score
painting, creative, art, create, artist, photography, nature, video, handmade, fashion, illustration, animation, drawing, artists, craft, digitalart, film, diy, artistontwitter, artwork, beauty,	Arts	.98
brand, branding, socialmedia, marketing, design, digitalmarketing, designer, designthinking, logo, graphicdesign, advertising, strategy, graphicdesigner, photoshop, digital	Branding	.95
mindset, motivation, success, mondaymotivation, growth, quote, quotes, love, life, inspiration, inspire, productivity, happiness, passion, work	Mindset	.99
business, entrepreneurship, innovation, leadership, entrepreneur, startup, science, stem, technology, startups, management, tech, ideas, future	Entrepreneurship	.98
writerslife, poetry, books, amwriting, author, writer, writers, writing, writingcommunity, storytelling, podcast	Storytelling	.88
fun, skills, play, imagination, learning, education, kids	Education	.93
music, diversity, community, culture, talent, arts	Music and Culture	.97
health, covid19, mindfulness, wellbeing, mentalhealth, blog	Wellbeing	.94
teamwork, problemsolving, curiosity, collaboration, communication, criticalthinking	Teamwork	.98
#Innovation-Clusters: Hashtag-Sequence	#1 Label	Score
digitaltransformation, automation, digital, security, cybersecurity, artificialintelligence, bigdata, analytics, cloud, iot, datascience, futureofwork, robotics, data, machinelearning, smartcity, coding, deeplearning, robots, python	Digital Transformation	.98
technology, creativity, tech, technews, designthinking, future, news, design, development, engineering, 3dprinting, art, software, manufacturing, mobile, construction	Technology and Design	.98
collaboration, ideas, blockchain, crypto, fintech, banking, cryptocurrency, community, finance, investment, disruption, bitcoin, insurtech	Fintech	.99
business, entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship, motivation, success, entrepreneur, growth, inspiration, startups, startup, smallbusiness	Entrepreneurship	.99
diversity, leadership, transformation, strategy, ceo, change, management, podcast, culture	Leadership and Culture	.89
science, research, education, learning, stem, edtech	Education	.93
ecommerce, retail, marketing, digitalmarketing, branding, socialmedia	Branding	.87
healthcare, covid19, health, digitalhealth, healthtech, medtech	Health	.96
sustainability, energy, sustainable, climatechange	Sustainability	.98

Note. Scores closer to 1 resemble a better fit of the label (cluster title) to the string (hashtag sequence). Arts would have been a very good fit for Culture and Music as well given that the hashtag “arts” is a literal match, still, Culture and Music was correctly identified as the best-fitting label considering the other elements of the sequence.

Table S2. List of locally dependent hashtags for both networks.

#Creativity	Dependency
<i>drawing</i>	<i>artwork, painting, art, artist, illustration</i>
<i>logo</i>	<i>graphicdesign, brand, branding, designer</i>
<i>marketing</i>	<i>digitalmarketing, advertising, branding, socialmedia</i>
<i>artwork</i>	<i>painting, artist, illustration</i>
<i>designer</i>	<i>graphicdesign, design</i>
<i>writingcommunity</i>	<i>writerslife, amwriting, writers</i>
<i>art</i>	<i>artist, painting</i>
<i>branding</i>	<i>digitalmarketing, brand</i>
<i>collaboration</i>	<i>communication, criticalthinking</i>
<i>graphicdesign</i>	<i>graphicdesigner, design</i>
<i>motivation</i>	<i>inspiration</i>
<i>entrepreneur</i>	<i>startup</i>
<i>writerslife</i>	<i>amwriting</i>
<i>socialmedia</i>	<i>digitalmarketing</i>
<i>author</i>	<i>writer</i>
<i>illustration</i>	<i>digitalart</i>
<i>communication</i>	<i>criticalthinking</i>
#Innovation	Dependency
<i>datascience</i>	<i>data, machinelearning, coding, deeplearning, python, artificialintelligence, bigdata, analytics</i>
<i>machinelearning</i>	<i>coding, deeplearning, python, artificialintelligence, bigdata, robotics</i>
<i>bigdata</i>	<i>analytics, iot, data, python</i>
<i>bitcoin</i>	<i>blockchain, crypto, cryptocurrency</i>
<i>healthtech</i>	<i>medtech, healthcare, digitaltech</i>
<i>marketing</i>	<i>digitalmarketing, branding, socialmedia</i>
<i>robotics</i>	<i>robots, automation, artificialintelligence</i>
<i>blockchain</i>	<i>crypto, cryptocurrency</i>
<i>cybersecurity</i>	<i>iot, security</i>
<i>python</i>	<i>analytics, coding</i>
<i>motivation</i>	<i>inspiration</i>
<i>entrepreneur</i>	<i>startup</i>
<i>healthcare</i>	<i>digitalhealth</i>
<i>artificialintelligence</i>	<i>deeplearning</i>
<i>crypto</i>	<i>cryptocurrency</i>
<i>fintech</i>	<i>banking</i>
<i>iot</i>	<i>smartcity</i>
<i>digitalmarketing</i>	<i>socialmedia</i>

Figure S1. Relative prevalence of #innovation-topics over time.

Figure S2. Sentiment and prevalence for hashtags contained in #innovation-network tweets.

